
**MEDIA EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PREPARATION OF
FUTURE TEACHERS AS A CONDITION OF EFFECTIVE FUNCTIONING
OF THE LIFELONG EDUCATION SYSTEM**

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Abstract. As one of the requirements for the effective operation of the lifetime education system, the article discusses the state and potential of media education technologies in the training of future teachers. The findings of the poll that was sent to teachers and students They are arranged based on how open they are to utilizing media-based instructional innovations in the classroom. Nevertheless, it should be remembered that technology is evolving at a quick pace, necessitating ongoing updating for these institutions and teachers. Focusing on the value and significance of classrooms that make use of technology is the primary goal of this effort.

Key words: lifelong education, media education technology, training, future teachers.

**МЕДИАОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ
БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ КАК УСЛОВИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО
ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ НЕПРЕРЫВНОГО
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

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Аннотация. В качестве одного из требований эффективной работы системы непрерывного образования в статье рассматривается состояние и потенциал медиаобразовательных технологий в подготовке будущих учителей. Результаты опроса, который был разослан учителям и ученикам. Они упорядочены в зависимости от того, насколько они открыты для использования образовательных инноваций на основе средств массовой информации в классе. Тем не менее, следует помнить, что технологии развиваются быстрыми темпами, что требует постоянного обновления этих учреждений и учителей.

Основной целью этих усилий является сосредоточение внимания на ценности и значимости классов, в которых используются технологии.

Ключевые слова: непрерывное образование, технологии медиаобразования, обучение, будущее учителя.

KELAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNI TAYYORLASHDA MEDIA TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI UMURBOQIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING SAMARALI FOYDALANISH SHARTI SIFATIDA.

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada umrbod ta'lim tizimining samarali faoliyatiga qo'yiladigan talablardan biri sifatida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashda mediata'lim texnologiyalarining holati va imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi. O'qituvchilar va talabalarga yuborilgan so'rov natijalari. Ular sinfda ommaviy axborot vositalariga asoslangan ta'lim innovatsiyalaridan foydalanishga qanchalik ochiq ekanliklariga qarab tartibga solingan. Shunga qaramay, shuni esda tutish kerakki, texnologiya tez sur'atlar bilan rivojlanmoqda va bu muassasalar va o'qituvchilar uchun doimiy yangilanishni talab qiladi. Texnologiyadan foydalanadigan sinf xonalarining qiymati va ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratish bu harakatning asosiy maqsadidir.

Kalit so'zlar: umrbod ta'lim, media ta'lim texnologiyasi, kadrlar tayyorlash, kelajak o'qituvchilar.

Introduction

Contemporary communication technologies necessitate a high degree of abstract thought, a fast reaction time, and a commitment to lifelong learning. This necessitates a broad enhancement of future teachers' professional preparation. As stated by A.V. Litvin, wrote, "To ensure that students have learned to distinguish reality from the information supplied by TV or other media, the teachers should use means of communication in the learning process in didactically appropriate, differentiated proportions with the objects of the material world (material means of education), ICT and other didactic means, employing the new technologies (in this case those of media education) in traditional teaching methods and technical means of education ...". Teaching students to digest information on their own, differentiate it, evaluate it, and organize it is the responsibility of educators. The media education technology itself is not a major component of professional teacher training; rather, it is the ability

to use it, perceive it critically, analyze it, and recognize the idiosyncrasies of its application in the educational process throughout life. This ought to promote in-depth study and sensible mass media communication use in one's future academic and professional endeavors. According to G.P. Vasyanovich, a teacher is morally and legally responsible for implementing technologies that are primarily intended to humanize human activities and raise future specialists' awareness of the nation's and humanity's development both now and in the future. These technologies are used in training and education. As the modern information society develops, a future teacher who is media competent should have developed media values, complicated media knowledge, and media abilities in order to instill media culture in parents and pupils.

Materials And Methods

Compared to their teachers and parents, today's kids and learners are more familiar with the Internet and mobile devices. This is a real trend in how the informational society is evolving. The responsibility of educators in the The goal of the informational age is to foster a child's capacity for critical thought, as well as their ability to evaluate and choose personally relevant information. They also want to help shape the child's media culture by organizing, synthesizing, and producing their own media texts for the informational environment. medium culture can be understood as both an aspect of an individual's overall culture and a component of the broader culture connected to communication medium. In order to shape the media culture of a contemporary adolescent, teachers should start with developing their own media competency.

With the aid of the educational program "Media Competence of a Teacher within Digitalization of Education," prospective teachers' media competency was formed through the use of ICT and mobile technologies. The curriculum was built on the "critical thinking" theory and practical theory of media education, which took into consideration the individual experiences and backgrounds of each instructor. Teachers with a foundational understanding of computers and a track record of utilizing mobile and information and communication technologies in their work were the target audience for this program. Through the use of ICT and mobile learning technologies, the program aimed to enhance a teacher's media competency in creative, constructive activities by creating a multimedia learning environment for a class. To achieve the program's objective, the following tasks have to be completed: The goals of media education as a field of pedagogical science are as follows: generalizing and systematizing current achievements in the field; mastering contemporary pedagogical technologies for the creation of educational media; studying contemporary pedagogical technologies, including ICT and mobile learning technologies, to create a multimedia learning environment for teachers to use media texts in their lessons; and mastering the

aesthetic and legal considerations when using media texts in professional pedagogical activities. Using ICT and mobile learning technologies, the assigned tasks were completed by working on distinct didactic and instructional projects for individual lessons, creating multimedia educational environments of the universal interactive hypertext space, and creating separate didactic media texts.

Results and Discussion

A person's motivational component is their integrative quality, which manifests itself in their willingness and preparedness as a teacher to examine media texts across a range of genres and themes, including non-entertainment genres. acquire new knowledge, look for media content for academic, scientific, or research purposes; be prepared to learn how to produce media texts independently using ICT and mobile learning technologies by examining particular instances of professional creativity.

The cognitive component includes the capacity and willingness to perceive, comprehend, and filter out "noise" from media texts; to recognize and value the power of media texts; to discern between rational and emotional responses when interpreting media texts; and to be aware of the linguistic quirks of various media and the ability to understand their impact regardless of the complexity of media texts.

The technological component include practical skills for self-selection, media creation and dissemination, and the capacity to utilize and choose what the media may offer. It also involves developing your own media product using ICT and mobile learning technologies. texts of different kinds and genres produced individually or in groups using ICT and mobile learning technology; the ability to actively self-educate in the media industry.

Conclusion

A modern teacher needs to be able to locate the information they need, traverse the information flow, fully perceive and assess media texts, and comprehend the sociocultural and political context of the media's operation in the contemporary society, to provide media-useful systems, and to code. The necessity to use ICT and mobile learning tools to help students increase their comprehension of texts and ability to process different types of information is driving an increasing amount of interest in the issues surrounding the building of media competence in future educators. The concepts of problem, project, and interactive learning form the foundation of the organization of the media education process. A variety of pedagogical approaches primarily draw on cycles (blocks, modules) of imaginative learning exercises. Teachers' development of media competency aids in the execution of the primary goals of media education: The ability to "read" and analyze media texts of different genres and spatial and temporal realities; the development of media perception, or the sense of media reality and the emotions and

ideas of media writers; the development of analytical skills related to predicting the impact of media texts on different audiences; the development of interpretational skills in the process of translating media communication into the "language of individual"; the capacity to decode information of media productions, including manipulative techniques and technologies; the capacity to create and distribute one's own media product using ICT and mobile learning technologies; the ability to choose, create, and distribute media texts New avenues for utilizing the instructional and developmental potential of media education in schools and universities are made possible by the study of contemporary methodological and technological methods of media education, as well as the history of their emergence and development.

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